

Data Management Plan

CNR Pilot: career progression at CNR in light of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment

GraspOS project (GA 101095129)

16 February 2026 - V1.0

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18679355

Authors: Provost, Lottie (lottiemiaprovost@cnr.it)

Abstract

Project summary: The European Commission and many research organisations in Europe have developed ambitious agendas around reforming research assessment and promoting Open Science. While there is a reasonably clear vision on the direction in which assessment practices need to develop and the way in which research needs to be made more open, the actual implementation of this vision is lagging and represents a significant challenge for most organisations. The need to tailor assessment practices to differences between disciplines, career stages, and research outputs further increases this challenge. The GraspOS project set out an ambitious goal to address these challenges, and one of the means to achieve this was to empower and bring together different stakeholder communities to co-design, showcase, validate and evaluate tools, services and resources supporting Open Science-aware responsible research assessment developed within the project in real-world pilots. (Himanen, L. (2025). Deliverable 5.3: Pilot findings and progress report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17035609>)

Project objectives: The CNR Pilot was one of nine pilots within the GraspOS project. It focused on career progression at CNR in the light of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (Arentoft, M. et al. (2022). Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13480728>), analysing the evaluation criteria of the 2023 competitive calls in relation to the Agreement's core commitments to determine whether they are aligned. The pilot also aimed to explore how the resources, tools and services developed within GraspOS, and more broadly, Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment, could support and improve the evaluation process in research performing organisations such as CNR.

Project ID: GraspOS: next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science (Grant Agreement n.101095129)

Start date: 01 January 2023

End date: 31 December 2025

1. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

The project re-uses official and public CNR documents, including four competitive calls (315.62, 315.63, 315.64, 315.65), regulatory attachments (A, B, C, D), and the evaluation criteria issued by 90 disciplinary committees, which provide the baseline for assessing policy implementation.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or reuse?

Re-used data consists of official regulatory documents.

Generated data includes an archive of PDF files collected via web scraping, the Python code used for data collection, and structured spreadsheets (Excel) containing researchers' analysis, annotations, and scores. Derived outputs may include statistical analyses, figures, and publications based on the structured datasets.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The project aims to verify how the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) commitments are implemented within the 2023 career advancement procedures for researchers and technologists at the National Research Council of Italy (CNR). The re-used and generated data provide the empirical basis to assess ARRA compliance in career advancement procedures.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or reuse ?

The study involves the detailed analysis of 4,090 individual criteria across 90 committees.

The archived PDFs are expected to require ~333 MB, the structured spreadsheets ~500 KB, and Python script ~24KB, for a total of ~333 MB.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or reused?

The primary data originates from the CNR Public Relations Office (URP) portal.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

This data is valuable for other Research Performing Organizations (RPOs), policy makers, and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) to understand the transition from high-level policy to institutional practice.

2. FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

The datasets are identified by a DOI on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18657087>), and the code is accessible via a public GitHub repository (<https://github.com/andremann/graspos-pilot-cnr>) and on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18649943>).

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Rich metadata is provided through structured spreadsheets that track annotations for the four ARRA commitments and Open Science practices.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Search keywords such as "Research Assessment", "CNR", "CoARA" and "ARRA" are used to optimise discovery.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes. By depositing the data and code in Zenodo and GitHub, the metadata is made available for harvesting through standard protocols (such as OAI-PMH used by Zenodo) and indexed by global search engines and research registries.

2.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Data is deposited in trusted repositories, specifically Zenodo for the analysis data and GitHub for the technical code

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Yes. The authors have already established repositories on GitHub (for code) and Zenodo (for datasets and analysis spreadsheets) to ensure public access.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes. Zenodo assigns a DOI (Persistent Identifier) to the dataset, which resolves directly to the digital objects (the spreadsheets and archived PDFs).

Will all data be made openly available?

All data is made openly available to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.

N/A

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

N/A

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Yes. The data is accessible via HTTP/HTTPS protocols through the Zenodo and GitHub web interfaces and APIs.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

N/A

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained? Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Identity ascertainment is not required, as the data is made openly available to the public without restrictions. The project does not deal with personal or sensitive data, therefore, there is no need for a data access committee.

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why.

Yes. In alignment with Horizon Europe requirements, metadata on Zenodo is typically licensed under a CC0 public domain dedication to facilitate discovery.

Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes. The metadata entries on Zenodo and the README file on GitHub provide the necessary context, URLs, and descriptions to access and use the data.

How long will the data remain available and findable?

The Python code is hosted on GitHub for public access and version control, but Zenodo DOIs ensure that the code and datasets remain findable and citable in the long term (Zenodo policy guarantees a minimum of 20 years of preservation). Original source documents are maintained on the CNR URP portal

Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Yes (same as above).

Will documentation or reference about any software needed to access or read the data be included?

The Python script necessary to replicate the data collection is included in the GitHub repository.

Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The Python script used for web scraping is provided as open-source code in the GitHub repository.

2.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices?

The data follows standardised formats like PDF for documents and common spreadsheet formats for analysis. The analysis uses vocabularies established by the ARRA and the CNR's Career Advancement Fields (CAF) classification.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Yes. The study uses the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) terminology and the CNR's Career Advancement Fields (CAF) classification, both of which are standard within the European and Italian research assessment communities.

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Yes. The data includes references to the official competitive calls (315.62–315.65) and the ARRA commitments.

2.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

A README file is included in the dataset to explain the methods to process the data, including the specific color-coding used during the annotation of criteria.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?

Yes. The data is openly available on Zenodo and GitHub.

Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Yes, as required by the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement, all data is deposited under a CC-BY license.

Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes. The data, analysis spreadsheets, and code will be openly available in trusted repositories (Zenodo and GitHub) under standard open licenses (CC-BY for data, MIT or similar for code). This ensures that third parties, including researchers, policy makers, and research performing organisations, can access, replicate,

and build upon the project outputs even after the project ends. The provided metadata, README file, and documentation facilitate understanding and reuse across disciplines, thereby supporting reproducibility and further research.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes. The provenance is documented by citing the original source: the CNR Public Relations Office (URP) portal and Zenodo.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Data quality was ensured through 15 collegial meetings where researchers discussed the criteria and reached a consensus in annotating the structured spreadsheets. The methodology is explained in Di Donato, F. et al. (2026). Mind the Gap, pre-print on Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18642800.

3. Other Research Outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

The project generated Python software code for web scraping, which is managed according to FAIR principles on GitHub.

A manuscript based on the analysis of these datasets is available as a preprint (Di Donato, F. et al. (2026). Mind the Gap, pre-print on Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18642800). This paper references the datasets and code hosted on Zenodo and GitHub, in accordance with FAIR principles.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above can apply to the management of other research outputs and provide sufficient detail on how they will be managed and shared.

The project generated a Python script for web scraping to collect PDFs of evaluation criteria. This code is shared on GitHub to satisfy the FAIR principles of findability and accessibility, allowing others to replicate the data collection process

4. Allocation of Resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

By using free public repositories like Zenodo and GitHub, costs for making the data FAIR are minimal.

How will these be covered?

The research is part of the GraspOS project, funded under Grant Agreement 101095129.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The authors of the study (Francesca Di Donato, Andrea Mannocci, Fabrizio Pecoraro, and Lottie Provost) are responsible for the management and analysis of the data

How will long term preservation be ensured?

Long-term preservation is guaranteed by Zenodo's infrastructure, which requires no additional direct costs from the project for public-interest data.

Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

No additional resources are necessary to accomplish this.

5. Data Security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Security is maintained by using trusted repositories (Zenodo and GitHub) which have robust protocols for data integrity, version control, and recovery. No sensitive personal data was collected, further reducing security risks.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes, the data is stored in Zenodo, intended for long-term preservation and curation, and on the CNR URP portal.

6. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

The research relies exclusively on publicly available regulatory documents and official institutional criteria.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

The analysis focuses on institutional criteria rather than sensitive personal data of the candidates, thus minimising ethical risks. However, if the project was to deal with this kind of personal data, project members would ensure informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation are included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, and that personal data is anonymised.